

Developing a mental well-being application for Filipino young adults: A pilot study and lessons from LUNA

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Long after the COVID-19 pandemic, the impact on mental health remains a critical concern – especially in the Filipino community, which continues to face challenges in accessing psychological resources. This study aimed to develop and pilot a mobile mental well-being application called LUNA, designed for young Filipino adults. The app integrates evidence-based tools such as mindfulness exercises, journaling, and mood tracking, which are known to reduce psychological distress and promote positive mental health. Filipino participants aged 20 to 30 were invited to use LUNA consistently over four weeks. Quantitative results demonstrated a significant increase in positive affect and overall mental well-being among users, though no notable change was observed in levels of negative affect. In-depth qualitative feedback highlighted user experiences, shedding light on LUNA's efficacy in supporting self-management of mental well-being. The study concludes by describing the dynamic relationship between users and the application, impacted by a network of interactive elements that ultimately influence mental health outcomes. Key lessons from LUNA's pilot phase offer valuable insights for researchers and app developers in the field, emphasising the importance of culturally sensitive design and sustained user engagement for the future of digital mental healthcare in the Philippines.

Keywords: application development; digital mental healthcare; journaling; mental well-being; mindfulness; mood-tracking

The COVID-19 pandemic, characterised by prolonged lockdowns and economic distress, has had a significant impact on the mental health of Filipinos. Studies have shown increased rates of anxiety, depression, and post-traumatic stress disorder (Cao et al., 2020; McBride et al., 2021; Rosen et al., 2020; Satici et al., 2020; Shanbehzadeh et al., 2021; Tanoue et al., 2020). Among Filipino young adults, academic disruptions, financial insecurity, and social isolation have been linked to heightened stress and feelings of hopelessness (Mendoza et al., 2021; Tee et al., 2020). These challenges are exacerbated by limited access to mental health services due to cultural stigma, economic constraints, and a shortage of mental health professionals (Lally et al., 2019; World Health Organization, 2018).

To address these issues, tele-mental health services, particularly smartphone applications, offer a promising solution to enhance accessibility and affordability of mental health care (Nijland et al., 2008; Zhou et al., 2020). However, more research is needed to identify and develop evidence-based mental health applications that can effectively meet the needs of low resource populations like the Philippines.

This study aims to explore the potential of an empirically based mobile application for the effective management of affect and mental well-being within a Filipino community. It emphasises the development of emotional awareness and self-regulation skills, which are crucial for maintaining psychological health. With the increasing reliance on digital technology for mental health support, ensuring that these tools are grounded in evidence-based practices is essential. This research contributes to the knowledge on Digital Mental Health Interventions (DMHI) in third-world, low-income Southeast Asian countries. Employing a mixed-methods approach that integrates qualitative and quantitative data, the study outlines the comprehensive app development process within this context.

METHODS

To assess the influence of the mental well-being application on the self-management of affect and mental well-being, the study employed a quasi-experimental one-group pretest-post-test pilot study design with the intervention being the regular use of LUNA, the mental well-being application, in their daily lives for the duration of 4 weeks (28 days).

Data analysis

To assess changes in affect and mental well-being, paired-samples t-tests were conducted using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) Statistics program version 26 on the International Positive and Negative Affect Scale Short Form (I-PANAS-SF) (Karim et al., 2011) and the Short Warwick-Edinburgh Mental Well-being Scale (SWEMWS) (Thompson, 2007).

The I-PANAS-SF, a reliable and valid measure of positive and negative affect, demonstrated adequate internal consistency ($\alpha = .78$ for PA, $\alpha = .76$ for NA) and convergent validity. The SWEMWS, a brief measure of mental well-being, exhibited acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .70$) and has been validated in diverse populations, including Filipino samples.

To evaluate user satisfaction with the LUNA app, a modified version of the Client Satisfaction Questionnaire (CSQ-8) (Mak et al., 2018) was administered. The CSQ-8 demonstrated strong internal consistency ($\alpha = .93$) and was used to assess user perceptions of the app's effectiveness and overall experience. Descriptive statistics were used to analyse quantitative feedback, and thematic analysis was employed to interpret qualitative feedback.

Participant sampling

The study participants were individuals who were 20 to 30 years old and residing in the Philippines during the pandemic. To be eligible, participants needed access to an Android smartphone and stable internet, no prior experience with mental well-being apps for the past 6 months, and no diagnosed psychological disorders. Participants were excluded if they belonged to vulnerable groups or tampered with app usage.

Participants were recruited through a combination of social media (Twitter, Instagram, Facebook, Reddit, LinkedIn) and snowball sampling. Based on best matches from the inclusion, exclusion, and withdrawal criteria, there was a target final sample of 30 respondents. The pilot study was conducted

in three batches of 16-17 participants. App usage entailed taking part in a short mindfulness exercise at least once a day, and inputting their mood and writing their journal entries at the end of the day. All three components must be utilised, and participants were encouraged to use the application daily and include it in their daily routines.

Choosing the components

Mood-tracking is based on Ecological Momentary Assessment, essentially the self-monitoring of psychological states (Rickard et al., 2016). Mindfulness is based on the widely accepted Mindfulness-Based Cognitive Therapy (Economides et al., 2018). Journaling is based on Reflective Journaling, stating that writing one's thoughts and feelings can lead to better emotional processing and regulation (Wang, 2021). These three are combined through a Gestalt Framework following the concept that the whole is better than the sum of its parts. Thus, a combination of these components, integrated into the mobile application LUNA, will hopefully lead to more positive results regarding affect and mental well-being.

For the first component, mood-tracking is based on the experience sampling method, and it involves the users choosing their mood by the end of the day and having their mood displayed for the past week (Bakker et al., 2018). The emotions ranged across a 5-point Likert scale from Very Happy to Very Sad, represented by a consistent set of emojis designed by the freelance artist as directed by the primary investigator. For a preview of the mood-tracking feature, please refer to Figure 1.

Figure 1
LUNA's mood-tracking feature

The basis for the second feature, mindfulness, is Headspace, a mindfulness-based smartphone application developed by Andy Puddicombe, a former Buddhist Monk (Mani et al., 2015). Some of these mindfulness exercises are available online, free, and open for public use and were incorporated into the application. The users will choose among various exercises in a video format ranging from one minute to ten minutes. The design of the mindfulness feature, as seen by users, is shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2
LUNA's mindfulness feature

For journaling, the users were provided options to do free writing or respond to specific prompts. The prompts were based on reflective journaling (Wang, 2021), which involves reminding them of the positive aspects of their life, understanding their stressors, and a daily reflection. These journal entries were automatically saved. For a better idea of the journaling component, Figure 3 provides a reference.

Figure 3
 LUNA's journaling feature

The application development for LUNA adhered to an Input-Process-Output-Feedback (IPO-F) Model, amalgamating essential stages from the framework proposed by Rickard and colleagues (2016). The IPO-F is similar to the Input-Process-Output Model, but with an added feedback component. This model is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4
 I-P-O-F model of application development

The Input stage marked the initiation of the process, with the primary investigator meticulously defining the application's minimum viable product. This phase addressed crucial questions about the application's intended functionality and visual design, paralleling the Pre-Development and Initial Development stages in Rickard et al.'s (2016) recommended steps.

Transitioning to the Process stage, the collaborative efforts of outsourced team members became prominent. The application developer focused on the intricate technicalities, coding, and constructing the application, while the freelance artist closely collaborated with the primary investigator to craft design elements such as the logo and splash screen. This stage aligned with

Rickard et al.'s (2016) Design Development and Software Development phases, relying not only on the team members' expertise but also on the available resources at their disposal.

Upon the completion of an initial product, the Output stage facilitated communication among the three key application development team members to manifest the primary investigator's envisioned mission and goals for the application. This stage was pivotal in ensuring a cohesive and unified approach toward the project's objectives. Subsequently, the Feedback stage ensued, where constructive revisions were implemented through a process of compromise and balance among the diverse perspectives and priorities of the team members. These revisions included refining design elements, such as selecting a breathing gif with a smoother frame rate to enhance visual appeal and relaxation and adding the side menu to ensure a more seamless and intuitive user experience. This iterative cycle persisted until the final APK was achieved, culminating in four distinct versions of LUNA.

In reflecting on this development process, several valuable insights emerged for social science researchers. Notably, the importance of reconciling terminology differences among team members was evident, as the researcher, app developer, and artist employed varying language conventions. Additionally, the feasibility of design decisions had to be carefully considered, with trade-offs being weighed and certain features prioritised over others due to platform constraints and limited prompts. The realisation that certain intended features were overlooked in the execution phase underscored the critical need for aligning theoretical concepts with practical execution to ensure the comprehensive inclusion of all planned features in the final product. The dynamic and iterative nature of the development process emphasised the significance of clear communication, adaptability, and a collaborative mindset to overcome challenges and achieve the desired outcomes.

User testing

Before the final APK of LUNA could be released to the pilot study's participants, it first had to be tested with preliminary users to fix any minor bugs within the application and to ensure its functionality. Therefore, nine users who had similar characteristics to the study sample installed and used LUNA every day for one week and took the App Functionality Survey. This survey investigated LUNA's performance during the installation process, when using the components (mood-tracking, mindfulness exercises, and journaling), and general questions and suggestions for improvement before launch.

It is important to note that the suggestions during the User Testing reflected the recommendations during the actual data gathering, and the inquiries users had during this period informed the questions on the Frequently Asked Questions document. All things considered, most issues were reported to the application developer and addressed and the User Testing demonstrated that LUNA was ready to be launched for data gathering.

LUNA's usage performance

Through a descriptive analysis of the experience of 30 respondents using LUNA for 28 days, LUNA received a reasonably satisfactory rating of 3.29 out of 4.00, with users being "mostly satisfied" with their overall experience and the amount of mental health that they received. Users reported that LUNA was able to meet most of their expectations of what a mental health application should be (3.26/4.00), and they found the components (mood-tracking, mindfulness, and journaling) to be somewhat helpful (3.29/4.00). In summary, using LUNA as a mental health application received considerably positive reactions, with more than half of users saying they would recommend it to a friend (60%) and would use it again (63%).

Within 28 days, the respondents had access to a web-based User Feedback Questionnaire, where they could answer guide questions and express their comments and suggestions about using LUNA. Their qualitative feedback was then analysed and categorised into themes related to application development and user experience, supplemented by the primary investigator's notetaking and observations.

More flexibility in mood-tracking

Participants in the study expressed limitations with the mood-tracking component, desiring more inclusive emotions and the ability to record multiple moods per day or edit previous entries. The feedback suggested a need for improvements to better mirror users' actual experiences, aligning with the importance of accuracy in Ecological Momentary Assessment, as emphasised by Teles and colleagues (2019). Notably, this study represents one of the initial efforts to integrate mood-tracking as part of a combined intervention.

Limited typing space

For the journaling component, most respondents observed that they cannot scroll up or down when typing their journal entry. This proved to be a frustrating experience that may have affected the effectivity of journaling as a component. This was briefly brought up by one of the users during the User Testing but, unfortunately, could not be addressed due to budget constraints.

Improve the breathing animation

Respondents provided feedback to enhance the mindfulness component's breathing exercises, suggesting additional instructions to differentiate between chest and diaphragmatic breathing. Users also highlighted challenges in synchronising with the animation's timing, proposing solutions such as a start button or customisable timing intervals. Furthermore, participants recommended incorporating calming music to enhance the overall relaxation experience during the mindfulness exercises.

Simplicity, straightforwardness, and convenience

The prevailing theme among users was LUNA's commendable design simplicity and straightforwardness, aligning with the principle that an uncluttered interface enhances user experience. Simplifying the design by removing unnecessary elements and prioritising core functionality contributed to a seamless transition between components, ultimately increasing user-friendliness. Additionally, users appreciated the convenience of LUNA, emphasising its offline accessibility, absence of ads, and minimal disruptions during use.

More personalisation of experience

In User Interface and User Experience (UX/UI) design, personalisation is considered essential for enhancing user engagement, as noted by Alqahtani and Orji (2020). Aligning with research in tele-mental health experiences indicating better outcomes with personalised interactions (Hind & Sibbald, 2014), LUNA users suggested various ways to tailor their experience. In the journaling feature, they proposed options for self-expression, such as personal prompts, customisable entries with stickers and emojis, and a voice recording feature. Additionally, users recommended an option to personalise the app's overall design to align with individual aesthetic preferences.

Minor Design Improvements. Users proposed minor UI/UX improvements for LUNA to enhance app performance. Recommendations included implementing an auto-saving feature in the Journaling component to prevent progress loss, adding an option to download mindfulness videos for offline use, and greying out unselected emojis in the Mood-tracking feature for improved user clarity. Additionally, users suggested incorporating a calendar design for both mood-tracking and journaling, enabling users to track progress and reflect over an extended period, up to one year.

Additional Features. Users recommended augmenting LUNA's functionality by introducing daily reminders for consistent tele-mental health practices, emphasising the importance of integrating the app into daily routines. Accessibility improvements were suggested, advocating for LUNA's availability across various platforms beyond Android. Users proposed an option for data export to facilitate backup and progress analysis, but this raises potential privacy concerns associated with account creation for data backup. Lastly, recommendations included incorporating more in-app information, such as tutorials for new users, a feedback section for user input, and motivational content to maintain user encouragement and motivation throughout their mental health journey.

In conclusion, Application Development involves a delicate balance and intersection of wants and needs; one user might seek one thing in their user experience (for instance, the simplicity of LUNA), while another might want the opposite (the complexities offered by personalisation). Part of the process is compromising these demands along with what resources are available while remaining consistent with the app's vision and mission.

Lessons learned from developing LUNA, such as the importance of intuitive design, scalability, and adaptability, have informed its potential for broader applications, particularly in tailoring digital mental health interventions (DMHIs) to diverse user groups (Relajo, 2018). This includes adapting the app's content, language, and features to accommodate cultural nuances, varying levels of digital literacy, and different mental health needs. For example, personalisation options can allow users to select culturally relevant coping strategies or adjust the interface to suit their level of technological comfort, ensuring a more inclusive and effective intervention. Equally important is the availability of resources to incorporate feedback effectively, ensuring that revisions and improvements align with both user needs and project objectives.

An additional layer to this is application development in the context of research, where concerns such as empiricism, feasible and practical methodology, and ethical issues like privacy and security become paramount in today's increasingly connected world. Work on LUNA continues beyond this study, incorporating these lessons to refine its features and expand its applicability to other populations and settings."

RESULTS

The study initially engaged 92 individuals through a recruitment form. However, 14 were excluded based on inclusion and exclusion criteria, 26 did not respond to follow-ups, and three participants did not submit informed consent forms, resulting in 49 participants for the 28-day intervention using LUNA. Of these, 12 did not respond to the post-test, four were disqualified due to app usage tampering (consecutive three-day inactivity, incomplete engagement with the three components, or random mood and journal entries), and three withdrew, yielding a dataset of 30 participants for the paired sample t-test. The entire process from recruitment to pilot testing took place between January to March 2023. Despite the relatively small sample size, the pilot study's research purpose was adequately addressed with a 32% participation success rate.

The participants, with a mean age of 23.67 years, exhibited a broad age range, with a majority aged 21, 25, and 26 years, while the rest included individuals aged 20, 22, 23, 24, 27, and 28 years. Most participants identified as female, constituting about two-thirds of the total sample. Geographically, the sample was diverse, with two-thirds residing in the southern region (Mindanao), mainly in Davao and Zamboanga, and one-third from the northern region (Luzon), dispersed across Metro Manila. Only one participant from the central Philippines (Visayas) was included in the sample.

Table 1
 Paired samples descriptive statistics

Pair	Variable	<i>M</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE</i>
Pair 1	PA Pre-Test	16.80	30	3.79	0.69
	PA Post-Test	17.83	30	3.00	0.55
Pair 2	NA Pre-Test	14.67	30	3.65	0.67
	NA Post-Test	13.90	30	3.72	0.68
Pair 3	MWB Pre-Test	17.78	30	3.05	0.56
	MWB Post-Test	19.16	30	2.03	0.37

Table 2
 Paired samples *t*-test

Pair	Mean Difference	<i>SD</i>	<i>SE</i>	95% CI (Lower)	95% CI (Upper)	<i>t</i> (<i>df</i>)	<i>p</i>
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Pair	Mean Difference	SD	SE	95% CI (Lower)	95% CI (Upper)	t(df)	p
Pair 1	-1.03	2.62	0.48	-2.01	-0.06	-2.16 (29)	.039
Pair 2	0.77	3.33	0.61	-0.48	2.01	1.26 (29)	.217
Pair 3	-1.38	2.80	0.51	-2.43	-0.34	-2.70 (29)	.011

A paired sample *t*-test was conducted to determine if there was a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of LUNA users after using the mobile application for 28 days. The results of this inferential analysis are displayed in Table 1 and Table 2, which indicated a statistically significant increase in mean scores between the pre-test ($M = 16.80$, $SD = 3.79$) and post-test ($M = 17.83$, $SD = 3.00$) for positive affect ($t = -2.161$, $p = 0.039$), with a moderate effect size ($d = -0.39$). With negative affect as the outcome variable, the results demonstrate no statistically significant difference ($t = 1.261$, $d = 0.23$, $p = 0.217$) in mean scores between the pre-test ($M = 14.67$, $SD = 3.65$) and post-test ($M = 13.9$, $SD = 3.72$). Lastly, the results revealed a statistically significant increase in mean scores between the pre-test ($M = 17.78$, $SD = 3.05$) and post-test ($M = 19.16$, $SD = 2.03$) for mental well-being ($t = -2.704$, $p = 0.011$), with a moderate effect size ($d = -0.49$).

The findings indicate that using LUNA for 28 days resulted in a significant improvement in positive affect and mental well-being among pilot users in the Philippines, but not negative affect. There is a notable difference between the pre-test and post-test means between those who reported and did not report psychological symptoms. Specifically, those who reported bouts of anxiety, panic attacks, and difficulty sleeping increased their positive affect ($M = 14.67$ to $M = 17.67$), decreased their negative affect ($M = 17.17$ to $M = 13.33$), and increased their mental well-being ($M = 15.91$ to $M = 20.23$) scores by 3–4 units more than the rest of the sample who did not report problems. This is worth nothing as it may have important implications regarding LUNA’s impact for clinical and nonclinical samples.

Thematic summary

Over the 28-day study period, participants accessed a web-based User Feedback Questionnaire to share qualitative insights on their experience with LUNA. These responses, addressing guided questions, were analysed alongside the primary investigator's observations and personal correspondence with participants. The analysis aimed to identify themes aligned with the theoretical framework, incorporating concepts of ecological momentary assessment, mindfulness-based cognitive therapy, and reflective journaling. Thematic summaries, juxtaposed with existing literature, offer valuable insights into the effectiveness of LUNA for self-managing mental well-being.

Benefits of reflective journaling

Majority of users found the journaling component’s features to be helpful because it allowed them freedom of expression without judgment. They were able to express what they were thinking or feeling in a safe, supportive space and get any frustrations they may have off their chest. Journaling also helped the respondents to reflect on how their day went; this feature was a way for them to organise their perceptions and process their emotions surrounding recent events. Through journaling, users can learn to identify patterns in their thoughts and emotions, which can help them make more informed decisions and better understand their reactions to various situations. These findings are in line with previous research that journaling promotes self-reflection, free expression, and organisation of thoughts in a more solution-oriented manner (Adams, 1990; Murnahan, 2010).

Pros and cons of mindfulness

A notable finding of this study is how the mindfulness exercises provided the most relief to some respondents but also the only component to make some users uncomfortable. By focusing on the present moment, Headspace's mindfulness meditation videos were able to promote a sense of calmness, relieve stress, and alleviate anxiety. This result is consistent with prior research that mindfulness-oriented applications improve self-efficacy and increase one's ability to manage overwhelming pressure or stress (Economides et al., 2018). Despite these benefits, it may not be suitable for everyone, as some users claimed that mindfulness and meditation were ineffective for them or made them uncomfortable. Because mindfulness requires individuals to be fully present in the moment, it can be challenging for those who are not used to it.

Self-management of mental well-being

LUNA demonstrated notable efficacy in achieving its primary objective of aiding users in the self-management of mental well-being. Users expressed increased awareness of their emotional states, attributing this improvement to the app's features, which facilitated more effective evaluation and proactive addressing of emotions. The personalised and inviting nature of LUNA set it apart from other applications on users' phones, fostering a sense of motivation for consistent usage. Despite acknowledging the challenges in incorporating LUNA into their daily routine, users found the experience rewarding, emphasising the value of dedicating brief periods to contribute to their emotional wellness. Additionally, users praised LUNA for its provision of empirically based mental health resources, which not only contributed to their well-being but also encouraged regular app use as an alternative to seeking resources independently.

LUNA's target users

According to the respondents, LUNA is seen as beneficial for those experiencing stress, offering relief to individuals overwhelmed by various responsibilities, struggling in demanding environments, or dealing with persistent overthinking. LUNA's components are also considered helpful for promoting emotional well-being, serving as an outlet for individuals finding it challenging to open or express their emotions. Additionally, the self-regulatory features make LUNA suitable for those who face barriers in seeking professional help, whether due to financial constraints or hectic personal schedules. In essence, respondents believe that LUNA has broad applicability, extending its benefits to anyone, including the public.

Building on these experiences from LUNA users, we learn that incorporating a more seamless and integrated feedback mechanism within the app itself would significantly improve the process. Rather than relying on a separate questionnaire, users could provide feedback directly through the app, making it more accessible and enabling developers to respond to concerns in real-time. This approach would allow for continuous, dynamic input that informs adjustments as users engage with the app. Additionally, building on the principle of ongoing development, future versions of LUNA should prioritise the ability to implement regular updates and new features through widely utilised platforms. This ensures that users can easily access the latest improvements, such as personalisation options, new mindfulness exercises, or enhanced user interfaces.

DISCUSSION

The findings indicate that the use of LUNA had a notable positive influence on the positive affect of pilot users in the Philippines and the moderate effect size is comparable to that reported in other studies (Howells et al., 2014; Wen et al., 2017). This outcome is also consistent with current literature supporting that mindfulness can positively influence positive affect (Howells et al., 2014; Mani et al., 2015; Wen et al., 2017).

This study also found that using LUNA had a statistically significant positive impact on mental well-being among the sample, and the results indicate a moderate effect size, analogous to that reported in other studies (Mak et al., 2018; O'Dea et al., 2020). This consistency in effect size implies that LUNA is as effective as other mobile applications and interventions in improving mental well-being, and these findings are consistent with a previous large-scale study conducted by Mak and colleagues (2018).

Integrating the quantitative data with the qualitative data, we can speculate on several explanations as to why and how LUNA has beneficial effects on positive affect and mental well-being. To begin with, we can observe that most respondents use LUNA through a linear process of tracking their emotions over time (mood-tracking), evaluating those emotions as well as their thoughts in daily situations (journaling), and regulating those emotional responses through a more psychologically functional lens (mindfulness). Thus, LUNA works best, and is defined as a mental health application, not because of any one component but through the effective combination and interaction of these components. Knowing this, advances in tele-mental health can investigate what other combinations of components can be done, how they can be translated into existing devices and operating systems, and what other features can be developed to account for the shortcomings of existing components. Moreover, it is worth looking into how existing components can be improved by modern advancements. For example, using a chatbot as a platform for journaling might give a more responsive and flexible user experience, and collaborating with AI technology can aid in personalising what mindfulness exercises to use according to preference and familiarity with mindfulness, and to aid in lessening participant discomfort. Chatbots and AI have been incorporated in similar ways across other mental health applications currently available for public use (Inkster et al., 2018; Zhang, 2021).

he analysis did not reveal a statistically significant effect of LUNA usage to the sample's negative affect. Literature surrounding the impact of mental health applications on Negative Affect are still inconclusive. For instance, Wen et al. (2017) found that mindfulness interventions had only small effects on reducing NA in their meta-analysis, with larger benefits observed in community samples compared to student populations. This suggests that the efficacy of mindfulness practices in diminishing NA may depend on participant characteristics and the intervention context. Furthermore, O'Dea et al. (2020) reported that single-session mental health apps failed to significantly reduce depressive symptoms, highlighting the challenge of achieving substantial reductions in NA through brief or generalised interventions.

On the other hand, Wang (2021) demonstrated that journaling significantly decreased depressive symptoms, pointing to differences in how intervention components operate. Journaling may better facilitate emotional expression and cognitive processing, directly addressing underlying factors contributing to negative emotions. Given these findings, it is possible that the components of LUNA are more effective in increasing positive affect rather than reducing NA and other symptoms of psychological distress. These patterns suggest the need to refine LUNA's components to more directly engage with negative emotional states, as certain components may emphasise fostering positive emotional experiences, which may not sufficiently target the mechanisms underlying NA.

User demographics and cultural factors likely played a role in these findings. The sample, composed primarily of young females, represents groups identified as at higher risk for stress, anxiety, and depression, as highlighted in the 10-year Youth Risk Behavior Survey (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2023). This heightened baseline vulnerability could make it more challenging for LUNA's current features to yield a significant reduction in Negative Affect. Additionally, cultural influences in the Philippines, where social support is highly valued for mental health (Montano & Acebes, 2020), might limit the effectiveness of an individualistic, self-guided app like LUNA. Furthermore, time constraints caused by overloaded academic schedules and societal pressures on students (Rotas & Cahapay, 2020) may hinder users' ability to fully engage with the app and form consistent mental health habits. These economic and cultural disparities highlight the necessity of tailoring applications like LUNA to align better with the specific needs, resources, and cultural expectations of its target audience (Ellis et al., 2022).

That said, does LUNA teach self-care habits, or does it only offer temporary relief? Previous investigations have suggested that mindfulness can teach and develop positive attitudes and self-regulation (Remskar et al., 2024). The thematic summary, particularly the theme on Self-Management of Mental Well-Being, suggests the possibility that LUNA can provide both, although the current study cannot determine the sustainability of the said relief or these learned self-care practices. Within the context of emotional self-regulation, it is argued that psychotherapy remains to be a highly personalised experience, and applications should be seen more as a complementary tool rather than a replacement or its own medium or platform.

Building on LUNA's ability to foster immediate relief and self-care habits, its potential for scalability lies in its digital-first design and accessibility across diverse populations. By leveraging mobile

technology, DMHI apps can reach users in both urban and rural areas, making it an ideal tool for addressing mental health disparities in low-resource settings. Embedding LUNA into public healthcare initiatives could create a low-cost, high-impact intervention, particularly as part of a stepped-care model. This approach allows LUNA or similar smartphone-based applications to address mild-to-moderate mental health concerns while reserving more intensive resources for severe cases, ensuring cost-efficiency.

Nevertheless, app development for business interests does compete with public healthcare (Chan et al., 2014; Costa et al., 2021). For example, some helpful features for LUNA were omitted due to budgetary constraints, and improvements recommended by users require resources to implement. This implies that the development of mobile mental well-being applications for the empowerment, self-recovery, and increased accessibility of specific communities becomes an issue of public interest, specifically a governing body's investment in mental healthcare. The same is true for the regulations and resources necessary to successfully launch LUNA or other similar DMHI apps as a full-scale public mental health tool.

Drawing parallels between therapeutic alliances in psychotherapy and human-computer interactions, the relationship between the user (patient) and the digital mental health intervention is influenced by interrelated factors on both ends, encompassing budgetary constraints, feasibility, and evidence-based design for the app, and the user's motivational self-efficacy, socio-economic background, discipline, and help-seeking behaviour. The relationship can be further personalised through technological advances such as artificial intelligence, brain-computer interfaces, and biometric incorporation.

LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE DIRECTIONS

The present study acknowledges several limitations in interpreting results. LUNA's release as a personally downloadable APK file, not publicly launched, hinders comparison with other mental health apps in terms of user engagement and functionality. Self-report measures and participants' personal circumstances could impact pre-test and post-test responses. Concerns about the accuracy of self-monitoring app usage arise, given individual interpretations of appropriate use despite explicit instructions.

The study suggests several potential components for future exploration, including physical exercise reminders, gamification, and more comprehensive data recording, such as monitoring biometrics, sleep, physical activity, social media usage, and musical preferences. However, ethical concerns regarding user data privacy and the current technical reliability of AI technology must be carefully addressed. Future research expanding LUNA's features could look into data export capabilities, ensuring that users' personal information is securely handled and that they have full control over how their data is used. Additionally, to enhance data privacy, precautionary measures, such as data usage agreements, could be integrated directly within the app itself.

As a pilot study with a small sample, the research provides preliminary findings necessitating replication with a larger and more diverse group. Future studies should employ sophisticated methodologies to explore interactions between variables, assess implications, and determine optimal app usage for maximising LUNA's impact.

CONCLUSION

The study addresses the persistent mental health challenges stemming from the COVID-19 pandemic, particularly within the Filipino community with limited psychological resources. This research explores the potential of LUNA as a mental well-being mobile application, revealing preliminary empirical effects on the self-management of affect and mental well-being. The study delves into the application's development process, from conception, design, coding, launch, and evaluation.

Through the IPO-F Model, the primary investigator was able to create a satisfactory mental well-being application and note further considerations for future researchers and app developers in the DMHI industry, emphasising budget constraints and multi-faceted nature of user engagement. Although there are ethical and technological issues to consider, investigating the integration of biometric data, sleeping habits, and AI-driven customisation could improve user experiences.

The study envisions contributing to the growing knowledge of concrete and self-sustainable tele-psychological interventions, recognising the evolving mental health landscape in an increasingly technologically interconnected world. As the mental health industry undergoes this transition, the study emphasises the importance of informed stakeholders guiding and investing in novel therapeutic approaches, especially in low-resource countries.

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